

Identifying bonds between people and spaces: a study of three neighbourhoods in Barcelona

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Abstract

In the research project PROHABIT, we have studied the importance of the sense of place in the urban transformations of three neighbourhoods located in the periphery of the city of Barcelona. In all three cases, local residents have been involved in a lengthy fight against the plans of the administration to radically transform their neighbourhoods. This resistance shows the strong bonds between people and spaces: their identity and attachment to the place, as well the ways to appropriate and territorialize the spaces they live in. A methodology together with the corresponding tools required have been developed to collect and analyse the information about the sociophysical characteristics of the three neighbourhoods, gathered from interviews, observations and reference documents. Among other findings, the study has revealed that in order to present an alternative to the renovation plans, the neighbours have felt impelled to construct an identity of the place – an image and a narrative of what they consider essential features and values to be preserved – created from personal memories and historical evidences. This identity has played a fundamental role in the final acceptance of their demands by the administration.

1. Introduction

Over the last three decades, residents in three neighbourhoods located in the periphery of the city of Barcelona – Plus Ultra, Trinitat Nova and Vallcarca – have been fighting against the various attempts of the city planning office to radically transform or even demolish their neighbourhoods (Figure 1). After a lengthy and steady resistance, the city authorities have agreed to modify the master plans to respond to the citizens' demands.

Figure 1: Locations of the three neighbourhoods in the city of Barcelona

In the research project PROHABIT we have studied the bonds that exist between people and the places they inhabit, which are behind the resistance neighbours have put up against the plans of the administration. The study has revealed the values and meanings that they give to the environment they live in, both to the physical spaces and to the image they have of their community. Terms such as “home” and “place identity”, “sense of place” and “territorialisation”, reflect the bonds between people and spaces. In order to capture their specific meaning in the three cases studied, it has been necessary to create an interdisciplinary framework which embraces architecture and urban planning, and environmental psychology. Likewise, it has been necessary to create a specific methodology and the required tools to undertake this interdisciplinary research on the lived space.

2. The bonds between people and spaces

People are bonded to spaces. In the field of environmental psychology and related social sciences, the study of the people and spaces bonds has given rise to terms such as place attachment and place identity, appropriation and territorialisation.

2.1 Place attachment and place identity

Place attachment is a multifaceted concept that characterizes the bonding between people and the places that are important to them. It encompasses affective (feelings and emotions), cognitive (thoughts, culture, beliefs) and functional (actions and behaviours) dimensions. In order to clarify the multiple meanings and definitions associated to the term, Scannell and Gifford (2010) proposed a tripartite framework consisting of three dimensions: Person, Process, and Place. The first dimension refers to the actor (who is attached?); the second to the psychological process (how are affect, cognition, and behaviour manifested in the attachment?) and the third is the object of the attachment (what is the person attached to?). Some of the positive effects of place attachment are an enhanced responsiveness within the local

community which favours civic behaviours and an improvement in the quality of life (Tartaglia, 2012). It could also have negative effects when a strong sense of attachment prevents the person from leaving a place (e.g. to work in another city), or contributes to create closed communities which become reluctant to receive newcomers (e.g. old neighbours perceiving new residents as a threaten) (Anton and Lawrence, 2014). Place attachment is and adaptive process, since people and communities, also the physical environment, are continuously changing. It seems to be stronger among the poor communities, and then weakens as they climb in the social ladder (Fried, 2000).

The place plays a key role in the construction process of an individual's identity. The term place identity was first defined by Proshansky as "A substructure of the self-identity of the person consisting of broadly conceived cognitions about the physical world in which the individual lives" (Proshansky et al 1983, p. 59). Place identity embraces "a complex pattern of conscious and unconscious ideas, beliefs, preferences, feelings, values, goals, and behavioural tendencies and skills relevant to this environment" (Proshansky 1978a, p. 155). Furthermore, this identity with the place changes because of the evolution of the individual as well as the transformations of the physical and social environments (Bernardo and Palma-Oliveira, 2012).

Place attachment and place identity are strongly intertwined, to the extent that in some cases it is difficult to distinguish between both. This is the case, for example, in Brown, Perkins and Brown (2002, p. 259): "Place attachment involves dynamic but enduring positive bonds between people and prized sociophysical settings, such as homes. These bonds reflect and help cultivate group and individual identity."

2.2 Appropriation and territorialisation

The concept of appropriation has its origins in Marxist thought and it was introduced in sociology research during the 1960s and 70s (Altman and Werner, 1985). In a moral and psychological sense, "appropriation" refers to taking possession of something, adapting it to the own needs, to express oneself through the things possessed (Serfaty-Garzon, 2003). At the early stages of the development of environmental psychology, in the 1960s and 70s, the term appropriation was used by French authors while their Anglo-Saxon counterparts used instead concepts such as "territorialisation", "privacy" and "defensible space". According to Serfaty-Garzon (2003), these three terms connote the idea of control of a space, while the notion of appropriation is not circumscribed to it. Territorialisation is associated to the control of an area by an individual or group who make an exclusive use of it; privacy refers to the regulation of the intimate relationships between the person and the world; and defensible space refers to those spaces that a community considers their own, and therefore, are willing to defend against intruders.

Proshansky (1978b) discussed the uniqueness of the term appropriation in relation to other concepts such as territorialisation or private space. In a social sense, appropriation makes others know that one has control over a space; in this regard, it can be equivalent to territorialisation and privacy. In a psychological sense, it

means to adapt a space to the needs of an individual. In both cases, social and psychological, the message that the others received is that this territory belongs to someone. Appropriation is a process based on duration, on continuity over time. This means, according to Proshansky, that appropriation is indeed a process of constant re-appropriation.

Appropriation is not limited to taking physical possession of a place, but it conveys the reinterpretation of the history, meanings and values associated to it. Therefore, appropriation means to do activities that were done in the past by others in one's way, while developing and actualizing oneself in the process. It is a process of interiorizing the knowledge and skills historically formed (Serfaty-Garzon, 2003). Possession, however, does not necessarily imply appropriation. Rather it is a process of transubstantiation by which something outside us becomes part of our private sphere, a process which implies a progressive transformation of the being (*un gauchissement de l'être*) (Sansot, 1978).

3. PROHABIT: an interdisciplinary research on the lived space

The purpose of project PROHABIT – carried out between 2015 and 2018 by a multidisciplinary team of architects, planners and environmental psychologists – is to understand the dynamics that underlie the changes that are taking place, in the physical and social structure, of three neighbourhoods in the city of Barcelona: Trinitat Nova, Vallcarca, and Plus Ultra.

A basic goal of this research project has been to study the sense of place and the feeling of attachment that have led the communities in three neighbourhoods, with different origins and social structure, to maintain an opposition to the renovation plans of the municipal authorities over decades. This analysis, therefore, has been carried out fundamentally from the present – although taking into account the historical evolution of each neighbourhood, from its most significant origins, those that are still physically and socially recognizable – and projecting it towards the future, as visualized in the urban projects and manifested in the expectations of the residents.

To carry out this study, techniques and methods of participation and communication have been applied to facilitate collaboration between professionals (architects, social scientists, among others) and non-professionals, in the processes of configuration of space in its multiple dimensions and scales. The techniques used have been:

- *Non-participant observations*, carried out by students of architecture and social psychology.
- *Unstructured interviews* with key actors (residents, planners, experts)
- *Workshops* with the participation of key actors.
- *Documentary analysis*, based on publications in the press, academic texts, and information extracted from digital media; study of urban planning plans and building projects.
- *Environmental analyses*, carried out by undergraduate and postgraduate students of architecture and environmental psychology, using various representation

techniques (photography, video, narrative, conceptual maps, diagrams and diagrams).

The structure of the information collected through these techniques was then analysed by the researchers and structure in the following manner (Figure 2):

- **Topics** are the studied subject matters.
- **Questions** arise from the topics to be investigated.
- **Facts** are a set of **Evidences** to validate or refute the **Questions**.
- **Evidences** are derived from the analysis of Interviews, Observations and Documentation, and from the information provided by participants outside the research team (Participation).
- **Place** is a space / building / object with meaning in relationship to an Evidence.
- **Concept** is a keyword associated with an **Evidence**.

Figure 2: Structure of the research methodology

In order to implement the methodology outlined above, we have created PROHABIT: MAPPER (www.prohabit.org/mapper) (Figure 3), a qualitative analysis tool that enables:

1. To collect and classify the information obtained in the fieldwork (observations, interviews, documents)
2. To analyse the information from a multidisciplinary perspective, with the participation of the researchers from the various disciplines involved.
3. To share with the community the outcomes of the analyses, with the purpose of obtaining new inputs from them.

Figure 3: Interfaces of PROHABIT: MAPPER

Following an inductive/deductive process, from the collected information to the analysed topics, back and forth in various iterations during the research, we came up with eight categories that capture the sense of place, in its different meanings: Community Building, Public Space, Image and Identity, Living styles, Participation and Engagement, Sense of Belonging, Signification and Territorialisation.

4. Case studies: findings of the psychophysical analyses

4.1 Vallcarca

The neighbourhood of Vallcarca began to emerge during the late nineteenth century and early twentieth century on the outskirts of the old town of Gràcia, now one of the districts of the city of Barcelona. The lowest part of the district grew along the edges of a water stream, with two hills on each side that makes Vallcarca one of the highest elevations in the city. Originally, it was a settlement of summerhouses – intermingled with humble self-built houses – that quickly formed a small town with orchards and gardens, built without following any urban plan (Figure 4). In the latter decades of the twentieth century, the population density of the area increased rapidly, and with it the economic and commercial activity. Since 1976, Vallcarca has undergone a process of transformation that, due to administrative and economic reasons, has continued up to today. For this reason, many residents have chosen to leave the neighbourhood, while others have been expropriated or forced to leave their residence. In 2016, the city launched an open competition to modify the existing master plan. The competition brief included some of the neighbours' demands, among them: the integration of the new buildings in the built and natural environments, the adoption of housing typologies that follow the traditional model that combines residence and work, with ateliers in the ground floor, the exploitation of the natural resources and the use of renewable energies.

Figure 4: Early settlements in Vallcarca, beginning of twentieth century

4.1.1 Place identity and attachment

The oldest residents miss their old way of living and remember past times with nostalgia. Some of them long for their old houses with patio, which they do not have in the new housing block where they have been allocated new residence. These patios were a place to meet friends, more reminiscent of life in a village than that of a city. This feeling of living inside and outside the city is still perceived as a sign of identity.

In recent times, groups of younger residents have arrived, many of whom are linked to social movements sympathetic with squatters, and they have led the defence of the neighbourhood's identity. Over the last years, these newcomers have developed a strong sense of attachment to the place that has been manifested through social, ludic and protest actions. Paradoxically, this group of new residents has appropriated the imaginary of the previous generation, claiming the return to a way of life based on the relationship with nature and the strong sense of community, in line with the current discourse on sustainable –environmentally and socially– environments.

During the open debates organized to change the existing planning, both the old and new residents have defended an image of the place that has become instrumental in the process of recovering an alleged lost identity.

The limits of the different areas of the neighbourhood are determined both by their physical characteristics and by the activities carried out in them by the various social groups. In fact, there is a strong correspondence between both. The area that has more evident and recognisable physical limits (due to the topography and that is has a same low-high typology of housing) have developed the strongest resilience, and a greater capacity for social mobilizations, whilst those areas whose limits are not so legible and have shown less activity and cohesiveness (Figure 5). Furthermore, one of the public buildings which has most contributed to creating a sense of place is the public library Jaume Fuster. However, many of the residents do not consider this building as part of their neighbourhood.

Figure 5: Identifiable areas along the central axis Vallcarca

4.1.2 Appropriation and territorialisation

The situation in which Vallcarca has remained during the last decades has led to the appropriation of many of the public spaces and buildings in disuse. The case of the so-called “Plaça Farigola” is particularly paradigmatic in this regard: an empty lot left by the demolished buildings has been transformed by the neighbours into a “village square”, where local celebrations take place. In this case, the activity makes the place. Similarly, other empty lots have been transformed into self-managed urban gardens. The graffiti that fills many facades is also a clear example of appropriation. However, in Vallcarca there are several associations with different objectives and with different visions about what the neighbourhood should be in the future, which are not always coincident. Because of this, some of these appropriations of public or private spaces have been seen positively by some of the groups and negatively by other groups.

The public amenities (library, urban gardens, basketball court, and squares) are places of socialization where different levels of appropriation can be observed (Figure 6). The public library, for instance, is a place where tourists and local groups like to meet, while other places, such as the basketball court, are felt to be more for the neighbours. On the opposite side, the self-managed spaces that have emerged on abandoned lots are considered as excluding by other groups, such as tourists or short-term residents.

Figure 6. Activity in public spaces

In relation to the transformation of the domestic space, the change from the low houses with patios to an apartment in a multifamily block has not always been well received by the neighbours. In particular, by those who remember that in the old houses they could place their furniture outside in the sidewalks, and take care of their own garden. Now they are unable to do all of these in the multi-storey housing block. To compensate this loss, some of them have place plants and continue to chat to their friends in the communal spaces that provide access to the apartments.

4.2 Plus Ultra

The Plus Ultra neighbourhood is a group of two-storey houses originally built in the 1920s, located at the foothills of the Montjuïc mountain, in an agricultural zone adjacent to a water canal which was then covered as the area became urbanised. The buildings are set along two streets making a Y shape that converge giving rise to a triangular square (Figure 7).

Figure 7: View of the Plus Ultra neighbourhood, 1961, before the urbanisation of the surroundings

During the second half of the twentieth century, nearby areas were urbanised in accordance with the General Metropolitan Plan of 1976. As a result, blocks of tall houses surround the original settlement thus transforming the settlement into an island in the middle of the urban fabric. This plan, and the later modifications of it, called for the complete demolition of some of the existing housing, necessary to complete the extension of the street network in the whole area. In response to these plans, residents have strongly defended the preservation of the original identity of the neighbourhood over the years, that is, of the street layout and the two-storey houses.

Finally, after decades of uncertainty, in 2015 the city council approved a new modification of the general plan that respects the existing urban and building structure. With this update of the general plan, the municipality expects a slow recovery process led by the private sector that will lead to the progressive renovation of existing buildings while preserving the character of the neighbourhood.

4.2.1. Identification and attachment

The two-storey houses give the neighbourhood a unique character. However, the physical and social deterioration suffered in recent decades has led many of the neighbours to leave the area. The new residents, most of them migrants, are not aware of the history of the neighbourhood nor of the fights of their predecessors.

The memories that the houses and streets bring back to the oldest residents are a manifestation of their place identity. The city council's final decision to preserve the original houses meets the demands of those residents who still hope to return to live in the neighbourhood they knew in the past. However, new residents do not share this identification with the place and many see the new urban regulation as an opportunity to obtain profit through the rental or sale of their properties.

One of the recurrent memories of the former residents is the vitality that commerce once gave to the neighbourhood. Most of the original housing had a shop or workshop on the ground floor. This contributed to animate the streets, now empty spaces without activity during most of the day.

The current settlement, isolated from the adjacent streets, facilitates the generation of a strong feeling of belonging (Figure 8). This attachment to the place is strengthened by social activities, especially by the celebration of the treading of the grape, famous in the district, which evokes the agricultural origins of the neighbourhood, when residents picked grapes in the nearby vineyards to produce wine.

Figure 8: Public areas in Plus Ultra.

4.2.2 Appropriation and territorialisation

In this long process which the neighbourhood has under the threat of disappearance, many of the older residents have moved away, being replaced by new neighbours, mostly migrants, who have found a neighbourhood in a state of deterioration. However, the older residents have continued in charge of the neighbours' association while the newcomers have either not found a way to become part of it, or are simply not interested in joining. On the other hand, the new residents have appropriated the public space with activities that former neighbours reject, such as organizing social gatherings in the central square or in front of the houses, and walking the dogs in the streets.

Municipal authorities have recently undertaken a complete renovation of the central square and the two inner streets but this has only contributed to accelerating the detachment of the former residents from the place. The original houses maintained a direct relationship with the street, which facilitated some of the domestic activities on the sidewalk, as was usual practice in the past. The uniformity of the renovated public space (Figure 9) contradicts the trend to personalize it that is observed in the sidewalks, in some cases transformed into private terraces (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Renovated central square

Figure 10: A sidewalk transformed into a terrace

An intense process of appropriation of public space has been favoured by the lack of connectivity of the neighbourhood's inner streets with the surroundings, with both positive and negative results. The latest planning regulations call for the creation of a new access to the isolated central square, by creating new connections with the parallel outer street by demolishing one of the existing buildings (Figure 11). With this measure, it is expected that exclusionary behaviours will be reduced.

Figure 11. Latest approved modification of the general plan, 2015

4.3 Trinitat Nova

Trinitat Nova is an example of so-called “vertical slums” built during the 1950s and 60s in the periphery of the city Barcelona to house the masses of immigrants who arrive to the city attracted by its industrial and economic development. At the time of its construction, it consisted of blocks of high-rise flats – very small and built with poor materials – separated from each other by empty voids, with no public services nor equipment, in an area isolated from the city and disconnected from the transport network (Figure 12). Today, the area is bounded on the South and East by two major

roads with dense traffic, Ronda de Dalt and Meridiana Avenue. The first one is part of the first road ring of the city of Barcelona and the second one is one of the main accesses to the city.

Figure 12: Trinitat Nova during the 1960s

Figure 13: Special plan for the inner reform of Trinitat Nova, 2002

In 1996, the neighbours' association took the initiative of creating a Community Plan with the purpose of refurbishing or replacing the housing stock which was by then severely damaged because of the use of aluminous cement in the construction of the structural elements. This plan not only contemplated the reconstruction of the damaged housing blocks, but it opens up a process of reflection and debate about the neighbourhood as a whole and about its future: the current situation of the population (education, health, jobs) and of the community (associative movements, integration of social groups, quality of life); the lack of connectivity with the public transport, and the integration with the city and with the surrounding natural environment. These participatory processes led to the proposal of an "Ecobarrio Trinitat Nova", an exemplary exercise of citizen engagement in urban regeneration processes and of collaboration between residents, technical experts and administration (Gea21, 2004).

After a long administrative process and based on the results of a competition, a reform plan was approved in 2002 (Figure 13), which included some of the proposals of the neighbours. In the meantime, the damaged buildings have been demolished and new housing blocks built to allocate the residents. However, the vision of a sustainable neighbourhood was gradually abandoned by both neighbours and administration as the main concern has become to provide new houses for the residents still living in the damaged buildings. Currently, more than twenty years after the deficiencies were detected, there are still residents waiting for a new apartment. The lack of connection with the public transport has been solved, and there are now two metro lines with stations in the neighbourhood.

4.3.1 Identification and attachment

The original population of the neighbourhood were mostly immigrants arriving to Barcelona from other Spanish regions. Housing blocks were quickly planned and built by public authorities, without too much care for public space, transport infrastructures and services. From the beginning, neighbours started to organize

themselves to get from the administration what they considered decent living conditions: paved streets and squares, public facilities (school, church, sports hall, etc.) and easy access to public transport. The need to defend their rights in front of the administration favoured, from the beginning, the creation of strong personal and social bonds and an attitude of solidarity among the inhabitants. In spite of this lengthy process of urban transformation, the cohesion of the social structure has been maintained, which has facilitated the preservation of a collective identity. However, the arrival of new social groups over the last years has undermined the social cohesion of the neighbourhood.

This is not the case for the new generations that have grown up with under a certain feeling of stigmatization because of the bad reputation of the neighbourhood (a place for drug dealers, with poorly educated people, and a high unemployment rate). This has led them to look for other places nearby to study, to work or to practice sports, away from their neighbourhood.

The characteristics of the site have marked the character of the neighbourhood, physically and socially. The existence of tangible outer boundaries (a ring road, a highway and a mountain chain) and the distance to the city centre have helped to create a sense of identity with the place, precisely because of its isolation. On a smaller scale, there are areas within the neighbourhood which are easily recognizable because of the street configurations and because the housing blocks built in different periods (Figure 14). Different social groups have appropriated these areas to a lesser or greater degree, giving each of them a special atmosphere.

Figure 14: Social and physical fragmentation in Trinitat Nova

On the other hand, the lack of a central space with a representational value is very much felt in the neighbourhood. The current central space does not really act as a social condenser and the area surrounding the central market has lost its vitality following the latest urban transformations. The lack of social activity in public spaces and an insufficient number of shops are considered by the residents as factors that weaken the link of residents with the neighbourhood.

Many of the recently created public spaces have not fulfilled the expectations and have become mere spaces of circulation. The areas with greater social activity are still the old areas that have not been affected by the latest urban plan. Older neighbours still remember landmarks that have been demolished in the course of the successive urban renovations, for example, “a clock tower” or a “water-carrying bridge”.

4.3.2 Appropriation and territorialisation

The community-led process to renew the deteriorated buildings and the neighbourhood as a whole led by residents during the 1990s was exemplary in many aspects. Former residents still remember this process positively. However, newcomers do not appreciate these achievements of their predecessors or simply they do not know about them. On the other hand, the slow execution of the plans to build new housing blocks and the various modifications suffered in the process have led to the disenchantment of many of the neighbours who were involved in the debates leading to the Community Plan and to the proposal for an “Ecobarrio”.

Many of the public spaces whose characteristics - use, form, materials and equipment - were initially agreed upon with the neighbours no longer fulfil the current needs. Due to a prevalent feeling of insecurity when these spaces were planned, certain decisions were adopted by that time to prevent undesired social activities in the public space that led to create impersonal spaces that have become mere circulation corridors. Some neighbours remember now the old central square, -which disappeared after the renovation because of its negative connotations, since it was the meeting point of drug dealers- as a pleasant meeting place, even though it was stigmatized in the past.

Many of the residents who were forced to abandon their old apartments consider that moving neighbours from a whole building altogether into a new one has helped to maintain the links between them. However, some neighbours miss the greater social interaction that was facilitated by the old housing blocks, with access through walkways and with a direct connection to the outdoor spaces. The close relation of the domestic private space with the outdoor spaces facilitated their appropriation by the residents. This is still happening in some of the original housing blocks, but it does not happen in the renewed areas of the neighbourhood, which in spite of being better equipped (gardens, ramps) do not show signs of appropriation. Generally, these new public interventions are perceived as over-designed spaces that do not invite to stay (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Current state of the Trinitat Nova

5. Conclusions

In each neighbourhood, residents have adopted various strategies to oppose the plans of the administration, which in some cases were very much aligned with the interest of private developers. In spite of the different historical origins of the neighbourhoods and the variety of the strategies adopted, in all of the three cases studied there was a common need: to construct an identity of the place to be defended against the future delineated in the master plans. This identity is a social construction created with personal memories and historical evidences; a construction that relies on the bonds that residents have forged with the places they have lived in overtime and their will to preserve them.

The different degree of renewal of the social structure in each neighbourhood plays a fundamental role in the sense of place, individual and collective. In Trinitat Nova and Plus Ultra, the older residents have led the response against the plans of the administration. Even though they have achieved that their demands are satisfied, it remains to be seen whether the new residents will strive to maintain the image of the place which the older residents have defended. The situation is different in Vallcarca, since the construction of a social identity has been mostly led by new generations of residents. Their case is an example of a re-appropriation of a place, by re-interpreting the memories inherited from former settlers, to create an updated narration of the local tradition adapted to the current trends (return to the community live, respect for nature, use of renewable energies).

The idea of a coherent and homogenous neighbourhood, both in the physical and social sense, does not correspond to the reality we have observed. Rather, there is a fragmentation in both cases as specific areas – with well-identifiable limits which give them a specific character – are appropriated by certain social groups (young people or families, local residents or immigrants). The opposite trend is represented by the need – expressed by representatives of all groups – to have a central space which becomes the symbol of the whole neighbourhood, a “main square” in which the collective activities which represent the community as a whole take place.

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